

D6.2 - Project Dissemination Report

Author(s): Philipp Cimiano

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Linked Language Data for Knowledge
Services across Sectors

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Author(s): Philipp Cimiano (UNIBI)

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D6.2 Project Dissemination

1. Introduction

This document represents the 2nd version of the report on dissemination activities carried out until month 24 of the Prêt-à-LLOD project.

The primary goal of dissemination is twofold: promoting the project's pilots and services, and identifying actions to promote their further exploitation. The second goal is to disseminate the work done by the scientific partners in the corresponding relevant scientific communities. Overall, dissemination of the project aims at ensuring an efficient and effective set of activities to maximise impact and awareness of the project among the research community, standardisation bodies, industrial key stakeholders, public authorities, policy-makers, entrepreneurial and investors ecosystem, and also a close collaboration with the European Language Grid, and cooperation mechanisms with the other actions and other relevant language technology (LT) projects, initiatives and networks.

In this document we detail the industrial and scientific dissemination activities of Prêt-à-LLOD - both those already conducted and those planned for the future.

2. Dissemination Activities

2.1 Scientific Dissemination

The academic research and education partners of the consortium (NUIG, UNIZAR, UPM, UNIBI, GU and DFKI) have a common interest in scientific dissemination. Publication in academic conferences and journals is also one of the most important mechanisms for ensuring that the insights gained from research in the project Prêt-à-LLOD are taken up and used in other contexts.

The publications produced by project members are summarized in Appendix 1. Overall, the project members have co-authored 63 publications overall, 24 of them at international conferences including NAACL-HLT, EAACL, RANLP, LDK, Global Wordnet Conference and LREC.

We would like in particular to highlight the clear success and associated visibility that PaL had during the LREC 2020 conference. The project presented 7 full papers as the conference in addition to 8 papers contributed to workshops. Further, 3 workshops have been organized by members of PaL at the 2020 LREC conference:

- Globalex 2020 Workshop on Linked Lexicography
- Workshop on Multimodal Wordnets
- 7th Workshop on Linked Data in Linguistics (LDL 2020)

In addition, the first textbook on “Linguistic Linked Data” by P. Cimiano, C. Chiarcos, J. Gracia, J. McCrae has been published by Springer in 2020.

Appendix 2 gives an overview of the scientific events that the PaL consortium has organized or actively participated in. Beyond the 3 LREC workshops mentioned above, the consortium has organized two further workshops, one collocated with COLING (Joint Workshop on Multiword Expression and Electronic Lexicons, MWE-LEX) and one with EACL (First Workshop on Language Technology for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion, LT-EDI-2021). Further, the consortium has been involved in the organization committee of LDK 2019 (and also of the forthcoming edition in 2021) as well as at the 3rd Datathon on Linguistic Linked Open Data and the EUROLAN summer school on the topic “Introduction to Linked Data for Linguistics”.

Table 1 - Industry partners' dissemination events

Industry-targeted event	Partners	Target Audience	Result
LT Innovate , 24-25 June 2019, Brussels Belgium	SWC	LT Industry	Held a workshop, collected requirements for the Business Stories
SEMANTiCS , 09-12 September 2019, Karlsruhe, Germany	SWC	LT Industry, Text Analytics, Machine Learning, AI	Contacts, Sponsoring, Co-Location of ELSE-IF
eLex , Sintra, Portugal, 1–3 October 2019.	OUP	Electronic lexicography	Contacts, sponsoring, present linking initiatives
Webinar - The Cross-Dictionary Sense Linking Platform at Oxford Languages	OUP	Electronic lexicography	Presentation of a platform developed within the Prêt-à-LLOD project. Gathered interest from various stakeholders
Webinar - Oxford Languages and Prêt-à-LLOD's Cross-Dictionary Annotation Tool	OUP	Electronic lexicography	Presentation of a platform developed within the Prêt-à-LLOD project. Gathered interest from various stakeholders
Handelsblatt Pharma Annual Conference, 12-13 February, Berlin, Germany	SEM	Pharmaceutical Industry	Presentation of Text Analytics Applications for Business Use Cases
Pharma Pricing and Market Access Congress, 19-20 March, Amsterdam, The Netherlands	SEM	Pharmaceutical Industry	Presentation of Text Analytics Applications for Business Use Cases

Health Care Business Intelligence/Analysis Conference (EphMRA), 25-27 June, Warsaw, Poland	SEM	Pharmaceutical Industry	Presentation of Text Analytics Applications for Business Use Cases
Future Pharma Conference, 9-10 September, Boston, USA	SEM	Pharmaceutical Industry	Presentation of Text Analytics Applications for Business Use Cases
Open Data Impact Series V: Open Data and COVID 19: 23rd June 2020, Online	DLX	Public administration bodies	Contacts, discussion of pilot plans, https://derilinx.com/open-data-impact-series-v-open-data-and-covid-19-2/
Irish Annual Open Data Conference, 2020: 2nd December 2020, Online	DLX	Public administration bodies	Contacts, discussion of pilot plans, https://derilinx.com/open-data-conference-2020/
Webinar - Presentation and Demo of Chatbot: 18th November 2020, Online	DLX	Around 50 Derilinx customers from around the world	Interest from various customers https://pret-a-llod.github.io/blog/derilinx-webinar-recording/

2.2 Industrial Dissemination Activities

The business partners of Prêt-à-LLOD (SWC, DLX, SEM, OUP) have successfully disseminated the results of the project in particular related to the business pilots at relevant fairs, exhibitions and industrial conferences. DLX has in particular focused on open data events. In addition, it has organized webinars inviting around 50 customers around the world to disseminate the results obtained regarding the developed open data chatbot.

SEM has been active in disseminating the results of the pilots at conferences targeting the pharmaceutical industry (Handelsblatt Pharma Annual Conference, Pharma Pricing and Market Access Congress, Healthcare Business Intelligence/Analysis Conference, Future Pharma Conference). OUP has organized a series of Webinars demonstrating the sense linking approach as well as the cross-dictionary annotation tool to relevant stakeholders. Finally, SWC has been present and disseminated project results at the SEMANTICS and LT-Innovate conferences.

2.3 Other Related Projects/Stakeholders

The consortium is taking into account the strategy set by the European Language Grid¹ to provide new resources and tools to the public grid, so that partners of Prêt-à-LLOD, acting as suppliers, can apply their policies and models for controlling access rights. The cooperation with the Helpdesk of ELRC² is additionally helping with IPR issues, as the legal terms for data and services are an integral part of such infrastructures. Towards this goal, there have been a number of meetings with the ELG project to discuss potential synergies and routes for collaboration in terms of making Prêt-à-LLOD services and language resources available within the ELG infrastructure. Prêt-à-LLOD has in particular shown presence already at the kick-off meeting of the ELG project to establish a working relation with the project. For more details on the engagement and cooperation with other projects from the ICT29b call, we refer the reader to deliverable D5.4.

Below we give a list of engagement activities that have taken place with other EC-funded project (ELEXIS in particular) and with the ELG project. We also list participation in events organized by professional organizations with strong industrial attendance. Finally, we list the participations in standardisation bodies; we note that Prêt-à-LLOD members have chair roles in three W3C communities strongly related to Prêt-à-LLOD goals and topics. These roles allow us to drive the agenda of these community groups and align them with the scientific agenda of Prêt-à-LLOD.

Table 2 - Dissemination actions with other stakeholders

Organisation/Project/Event	Means	Partners	Date (DD.MM.YYYY)
Engagement with other EC-funded projects			
ELEXIS	Participation in Observer Event	NUIG/DFKI	18.02-20.02.2019
ELEXIS	Meeting with JSI and Elexis	DFKI	12.07.2019
ICT29b projects	Telco with other ICT29b projects	DFKI	5.8.2019
NexusLinguarum	Joint organisation of the EUROLAN'21 training school	UNIZAR, NUIG, GUF, DFKI	8-1.02.2021
Liaison with European Language Grid			
ELG	Participation at kickoff meeting in order to establish a communication line between the ELG and Prêt-à-LLOD, especially with the industrial partners of ELG, Expert System, SailLabs and Tilde	DFKI	22.01-23.01.2019
ELG	Tele-conference with ELG project and other projects accepted in the 29b call	DFKI/NUIG	18.3.2019

¹ <https://www.european-language-grid.eu/>

² <http://www.lr-coordination.eu/helpdesk>

ELG	Tele-conference with ELG project on the integration of Prêt-à-LLOD outcomes in ELG	UNIBI	09.07.2019 17.07.2019
ELG	Tele-conference with ELG project and other projects accepted in the 29b call	DFKI/NUIG	21.06.2019
ELG	Tele-conference with ELG project and other projects accepted in the 29b call	NUIG/DFKI	03.05.2019
ELG	Tele-conference with the ELG project on extension and harmonization of models for metadata for LRs.	DFKI/NUIG/UPM/UNIZAR	09.05.2019
Events with Industrial Participation			
7th Language Technology Industry Summit	Language resources taxonomy building workshop at LTI Summit	SWC	25.06.2019
BDV PPP Meetup 2019	2 Presentations by Prêt-à-LLOD	DFKI, UPM	26-28.06.2019
1st International Conference on the European Industry on Language Technology	Chair and Participation	SWC/SEM	09.09.2019
CrossLang (SMART 2016/0103 Lot 2 Service Contract for DG Connect)	Workshop "Showcase H2020 and INEA" organized by CrossLang (in the context of the SMART 2016/0103 Lot 2 service contract for DG Connect). Beyond this workshop, cooperation between Prêt-à-LLOD and CEF activities, like the SMART 2016/0103 Lot 2 service contract for DG Connect.	NUIG, DFKI	26.04.2019
Meta-Forum (organized by ELG)	Session on "Sustainability" co-organized by DFKI and NUIG, with ELG. participation at the pre-conference ELG technical meeting	NUIG/UPM	07.10-10.10.2019
Publications Office of the European Union Directorate A – Information Management A.1 – Standardisation	Participation in the workshop "Semantic interoperability for the multilingual web"	NUIG	4.-5.6.2019

Participation in Standardization Bodies			
W3C Ontolex Community Group	Chairs	UNIBI/UPM/ UNIZAR	2014 - to date
W3C LD4LT community group	Chairs	UNIBI/UNIZ AR/GU	2019 - to date
W3C ODRL Community Group	Chair	UPM	2019 - to date

3. Dissemination Tools

Prêt-à-LLOD is making full use of existing communication channels, such as major conferences and journals and exploiting its own dissemination channels, including the project website and the organisation of specific events, and the academic and professional networks of the partners.

A tangible dissemination tool is the Prêt-à-LLOD project website, which is continuously updated and will contain relevant project information such as [published reports, papers](#)³ as well as software and demonstrations made available to the research community, using visualisations and animations. The most important element here are demonstrations which can show how the language technology would work in real life. The website is an easily accessible and frequently updated repository for content produced by the project. It is thus a point of reference for project activities from an organisational, promotional and dissemination point of view and a means of interaction between the community members to reinforce ties and collaboration. The website also includes and maintains a blog where articles on topics with a strong reference to Prêt-à-LLOD are frequently published.

Web site visitors are encouraged to contribute to the dissemination of project results using a range of social networks, i.e. Twitter is used to assemble an interested community. Regular tweets about “news” on the website and within the research domain raises attention for the project and helps to find and build up a relevant community of followers.

Further tools for dissemination of project results include beneficiaries’ own websites and usual channels for keeping contact with clients/partners/users and use of social media, public and members monthly e-newsletters, and mailing lists to disseminate project information to key stakeholders.

The consortium is exceptionally active in the organization of major community events and these forums are both supported by the project in terms of support for the organization and supporting travel for speakers, and also are a crucial part of the community building.

Extra funds have been allocated to this task that are used to support the following:

- SEMANTICS conference (2019, 2020, 2021): SWC, SEM
- Language Data and Knowledge (LDK) Conference (Germany, 2019; Spain, 2021): NUIG, UNIBI, GU
- Summer Datathon on Linguistic Linked Open Data (Germany, 2019; TBD, 2021): GU, UNIZAR, NUIG, UNIBI
- Linked Data in Linguistics (LDL) workshop (2020; GU, NUIG, UNIZAR, DFKI)

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/Prêt-à-LLOD>

- Semantic Deep Learning (SemDeep) workshop (2019; DFKI) co-located at international conferences
- TIAD (Translation Inference Across Dictionaries) shared task (2019, 2020, 2021), UNIZAR, co-located at international conferences
- Open Data Impact Series : (April 2019, October 2019; DLX)
- Dedicated session (seminar/panel/workshop) on language data at International Open Data
- Conference (IODC) 2019 organized by ODI Madrid (UPM).

A list of target events and international journals and planned participation has been drafted and agreed by project partners at an early stage in the Dissemination/Communication Plan and kept updated during the project lifetime. Participation in external events includes presentations of scientific publications and articles, and the distribution of dissemination material and collaterals. High-level dissemination of the project results are conducted through workshops, including presentations to selected groups of enterprises and organisations followed by discussions and demonstration of business cases.

Dissemination through the above-mentioned channels is being achieved thanks to several dissemination supporting tools implemented by the consortium, including: (i) Project Logo, PowerPoint templates, templates for deliverables and general documents which were designed in the very initial phase of the project; (ii) Collaterals and dissemination material, including a project fact-sheet, poster and brochure; (iii) audiovisual material, such as walkthrough videos to show the pilots; (iv) Press releases, announcing the key milestones of the project; (v) e-Newsletters and posts on social networks to raise awareness about project activities; (vi) Contributions to magazines related to data analytics markets, European and national technical magazines, newspapers and/or other media channels have been explored.

Table 3 - Dissemination tool and target group

Tool	Target group
Website	General public, Professional / Research audience
Blog	General public, Professional / Research audience
SEO	General public, Professional / Research audience
Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn	Professional / Research audience
Newsletter	General public, Professional / Research audience
Flyer	Event participants and visitors
Poster (roll-up)	Event participants and visitors
Videos (on Youtube)	General public, Professional / Research audience
Walkthrough	Professional / Research audience
Hackathon / Datathon	Entrepreneurs and scholars

Workshop	Professional / Research audience
Scientific publications in Journals/Conferences	Research community (open access)

In addition, in order to efficiently spread excellence and disseminate knowledge, the majority of project deliverables and other formal commitments will be given a public level of dissemination.

4. Summary

The project is progressing according to plan regarding the dissemination of project results. From a scientific point of view, the project is having substantial impact within the scientific community, disseminating the results very actively at relevant conferences, workshops, but also through the organisation and participation in educational events including summer schools, hackathons etc. So far, the project has published 63 publications, 24 of them at international conferences. The goal of the project was to publish overall 20 articles in conferences, so that the goal has already been reached. We would like to highlight in particular our success at the LREC conference with the consortium having presented a total of 15 papers (7 at the main conference, 8 at workshops) and having organized 3 workshops. The visibility and scientific impact has thus been substantial at LREC, arguably the most relevant conference in terms of research topics for PaL. The consortium has also been very active in organizing conferences (LDK), workshop and datathon / summer school on the research topics of PaL.

The industrial dissemination has also been successful with the industrial partners having presented results from the business pilots at industry-related events, exhibitions and fairs.

Appendix 1 - Prêt-à-LLOD publications at M24

Publication	Author(s)	Conference/Journal
Extending Neural Question Answering with Linguistic Input Features	Fabian Hommel, Matthias Orlikowski, Philipp Cimiano, Matthias Hartung	Proc. of 5th Workshop on Semantic Deep Learning (SemDeep) at IJCAI 2019, BEST PAPER AWARD!
Zero-Shot Cross-Lingual Opinion Target Extraction	Soufian Jebbara, Philipp Cimiano	Proceedings of the Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, NAACL-HLT 2019
Porting Multilingual	Thierry Declerck, Stefania	Proceedings of the

Morphological Resources to OntoLex-Lemon	Racioppa	International Conference Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing, RANLP 2019
Towards the Detection and Formal Representation of Semantic Shifts in Inflectional Morphology	Dagmar Gromann, Thierry Declerck	Proceedings of the 2nd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge (LDK 2019)
Results of the Translation Inference Across Dictionaries 2019 Shared Task	Jorge Gracia, Besim Kabashi, Ilan Kernerman, Marta Lanau-Coronas, Dorielle Lonke	Proceedings of TIAD-2019 Shared Task – Translation Inference Across Dictionaries, co-located with LDK 2019
Proceedings of TIAD-2019 Shared Task – Translation Inference Across Dictionaries, co-located with LDK 2019	Jorge Gracia, Besim Kabashi, Ilan Kernerman (Editors)	
OntoLex as a possible Bridge between WordNets and full lexical Descriptions	Thierry Declerck, Melanie Siegel, Dagmar Gromann	Proceedings of the 10th Global WordNet Conference
Using OntoLex-Lemon for Representing and Interlinking German Multiword Expressions in OdeNet and MMORPH	Thierry Declerck, Melanie Siegel and Stefania Racioppa	Proceedings of the Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and WordNet (MWE-WN 2019), co-located with ACL 2019
Proceedings of the Poster Session of the 2nd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge (LDK-PS 2019),	Thierry Declerck, John P. McCrae (Editors)	2020
The Use of an Infrastructure for Lexicography in the field of Terminology	Tanja Wissik, Thierry Declerck	Proceedings of the 13th TOTh International Conference (held in 2019, published in 2020)
Adapting Term Recognition to an Under-Resourced Language: the Case of Irish	John P. McCrae, Adrian Doyle	Celtic Language Technology Workshop 2019
WordNet Gloss Translation for Under-resourced Languages using Multilingual Neural Machine Translation	Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi; Mihael Arcan; John P. McCrae	Moment Workshop
Multilingual Multimodal Machine Translation for Dravidian Languages utilizing Phonetic Transcription	Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi; Ruba Priyadarshini; Bernardo Stearns; Arun Jayapal; S Srivedy; Mihael Arcan; Manel	2nd Workshop on Technologies for MT of Low Resource Languages (LoResMT 2019)

	Zarrouk; John P. McCrae	
Identification of Adjective-Noun Neologisms using Pretrained Language Models	John P. McCrae	Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and WordNet (MWE-WN 2019) at ACL 2019
English WordNet 2019 -- An Open-Source WordNet for English	John P. McCrae; Alexandre Rademaker; Francis Bond; Ewa Rudnicka; Christiane Fellbaum	10th Global WordNet Conference – GWC 2019
Validating the OntoLex-lemon lexicography module with K Dictionaries' multilingual data	Julia Bosque-Gil, Dorielle Lonke, Jorge Gracia, and Ilan Kernerman	6th biennial conference on electronic lexicography, eLex 2019
Challenges for the Representations for Morphology in Ontology Lexicons [Poster]	Bettina Klimek, John P. McCrae, Maxim Ionov, James K. Tauber, Christian Chiarcos, Julia Bosque-Gil and Paul Buitelaar	6th biennial conference on electronic lexicography, eLex 2019
Porting a Crowd-Sourced German Lexical Semantics Resource to Ontolex-Lemon	Thierry Declerck, Melanie Siegel	6th biennial conference on electronic lexicography, eLex 2019
Enriching Open Multilingual Wordnets with Morphological Features	Thierry Declerck, Stefania Racioppa.	6th Italian Conference on Computational Linguistics, CLIC-it 2019
Linguistic Linked Open Data for All	John McCrae, Thierry Declerck	International Conference Language Technologies for All, LT4All, 2019
Linguistic Linked Data: Representation, Generation and Applications	Philipp Cimiano, Christian Chiarcos, John McCrae, Jorge Gracia	[Book by Springer, 2020]
Towards an Extension of the Linking of the Open Dutch WordNet with Dutch Lexicographic Resources	Thierry Declerck	2020 Globalex Workshop on Linked Lexicography (at LREC)
Adding Pronunciation Information to Wordnets	Thierry Declerck, Lenka Bajcetic, Melanie Siegel	2020 Workshop on Multimodal Wordnets (MMW2020) (at LREC)

On the Linguistic Linked Open Data Infrastructure	Christian Chiarcos, Bettina Klimek, Christian Fäth, Thierry Declerck, John P. McCrae	1st International Workshop on Language Technology Platforms (at LREC)
Recent Developments for the Linguistic Linked Open Data Infrastructure	Thierry Declerck, John McCrae, Matthias Hartung, Jorge Gracia, Christian Chiarcos, Elena Montiel, Philipp Cimiano, Artem Revenko, Roser Saurí, Deirdre Lee, Stefania Racioppa, Jamal Nasir, Matthias Orlikowski, Marta Lanau-Coronas, Christian Fäth, Mariano Rico, Mohammad Fazleh Elahi, Maria Khvalchik, Meritxell Gonzalez, Katharine Cooney	Twelfth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)
Modelling Frequency and Attestations for OntoLex-Lemon	Christian Chiarcos, Maxim Ionov, Jesse de Does, Katrien Depuydt, Anas Fahad Khan, Sander Stolk, Thierry Declerck, John Philip McCrae	2020 Globalex Workshop on Linked Lexicography (at LREC)
Graph Exploration and Cross-lingual Word Embeddings for Translation Inference Across Dictionaries	Marta Lanau-Coronas, Jorge Gracia	2020 Globalex Workshop on Linked Lexicography (at LREC)
Expressing Linguistic Restrictions in Terminologies	Thierry Declerck, Tanja Wissik, Stefania Racioppa	2020 TOTH (Terminology & Ontology: Theories and application)
Automated Formalisation of unstructured Terminologies	Thierry Declerck, Tanja Wissik	2020 TOTH (Terminology & Ontology: Theories and application) 2020
Interlinking Slovene Language Data	Lenka Bajcetic, Thierry Declerck	2020 Euralex (published 2020 in proceedings, to be presented in September 2021)
Principled Quality Estimation for Dictionary Sense Linking	Julian Grosse, Roser Saurí	2020 Euralex (published 2020 in proceedings, to be presented in September 2021)

XD-AT: A Cross-Dictionary Annotation Tool	Meritxell González, Charlotte Buxton, Roser Saurí	2020 Euralex (published 2020 in proceedings, to be presented in September 2021)
Determining Differences of Granularity between Cross-Dictionary Linked Senses	Eirini Kouvara, Meritxell González, Julian Grosse, Roser Saurí	2020 Euralex (published 2020 in proceedings, to be presented in September 2021)
Multimodal Meme Dataset (MultiOFF) for Identifying Offensive Content in Image and Text	Suryawanshi, S., Chakravarthi, B.R., Arcan, M. and Buitelaar, P.	5th Workshop on Indian Language Data: Resources and Evaluation, colocated with LREC 2020
A Dataset for Troll Classification of Tamil Memes	Suryawanshi, S., Chakravarthi, B.R., Verma, P., Arcan, M., McCrae, J.P. and Buitelaar, P.	2nd Workshop on Trolling, Aggression and Cyberbullying, colocated with LREC 2020
Defying Wikidata: Validation of terminological relations in the web of data	Patricia Martín-Chozas, Sina Ahmadi, Elena Montiel-Ponsoda.	Twelfth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)
Creation and Enrichment of a Terminological Knowledge Graph in the Legal Domain	Patricia Martín-Chozas	Doctoral Consortium co-located with 3rd International Conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems
Terme-à-LLOD: Simplifying the Conversion and Hosting of Terminological Resources as Linked Data	Maria Pia di Buono, Philipp Cimiano, Mohammad Fazleh Elahi and Frank Grimm	7th Workshop on Linked Data in Linguistics (LDL 2020): Building tools and infrastructure, colocated with LREC 2020
Proceedings of 7th Workshop on Linked Data in Linguistics (LDL 2020) co-located at LREC 2020.	Maxim Ionov, John P. McCrae, Christian Chiarcos, Thierry Declerck, Julia Bosque-Gil, Jorge Gracia (Editors)	2020
Proceedings of the LREC 2020 Workshop on Multimodal Wordnets	Thierry Declerck, Itziar Gonzalez-Dios, German Rigau (eds.)	2020
Proceedings of Globalex 2020 Workshop on Linked Lexicography co-located at LREC 2020.	Ilan Kernerman, Simon Krek, John P. McCrae, Jorge Gracia, Sina Ahmadi and Besim Kabashi (Editors)	2020
Figure Me Out: A Gold Standard Dataset for Metaphor Interpretation	Zayed et al.	Twelfth International Conference on Language

		Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)
The ACoLi Dictionary Graph	Christian Chiarcos, Christian Fäth and Maxim Ionov	Twelfth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)
Fintan - Flexible, Integrated Transformation and Annotation eEngineering	Christian Fäth, Christian Chiarcos, Björn Ebbrecht and Maxim Ionov	Twelfth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)
A Tree Extension for CoNLL-RDF	Christian Chiarcos and Luis Glaser	Twelfth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)
Annotation Interoperability for the Post-ISOCat Era	Christian Chiarcos, Christian Fäth and Frank Abromeit	Twelfth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)
Translation Inference by Concept Propagation	Chiarcos, Christian, Schenk, Niko and Fäth, Christian	Proceedings of the 2020 Globalex Workshop on Linked Lexicography
Towards an Interoperable Ecosystem of AI and LT Platforms: A Roadmap for the Implementation of Different Levels of Interoperability	Georg Rehm, Dimitris Galanis, Penny Labropoulou, Stelios Piperidis, Martin Weiß, Ricardo Usbeck, Joachim Köhler, Miltos Deligiannis, Katerina Gkirtzou, Johannes Fischer, Christian Chiarcos, Nils Feldhus, Julian Moreno-Schneider, Florian Kintzel, Elena Montiel, Víctor Rodríguez Doncel, John Philip McCrae, David Laqua, Irina Patricia Theile, Christian Dittmar, Kalina Bontcheva, Ian Roberts, Andrejs Vasiljevs, Andis Lagzdīņš	Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Language Technology Platforms (IWLTP-2020)
NUIG at SemEval-2020 Task 12: Pseudo Labelling for Offensive Content Classification	Shardul Suryawanshi, Mihael Arcan and Paul Buitelaar	Proceedings of SemEval-2020, collocated with COLING
Leveraging Linguistic Linked Data for Cross-Lingual Model Transfer in the Pharmaceutical Domain	Jorge Gracia, Christian Fäth, Matthias Hartung, Max Ionov, Julia Bosque-Gil, Susana Verissimo, Christian Chiarcos, Matthias Orlikowski	Proceedings of the International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC 2020) -- In-use track

Overview of the track on Sentiment Analysis for Dravidian Languages in Code-Mixed Text	Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi, Ruba Priyadharshini, Vigneshwaran Muralidaran, Shardul Suryawanshi, Navya Jose, Elizabeth Sherly and John P. McCrae	Proceedings of Hate Speech and Offensive Content Identification in Indo-European Languages (HASOC 2020), (2020)
iLOD: InterPlanetary File System based Linked Open Data Cloud	Jamal A. Nasir and John P. McCrae	Proceedings of MEPDaW'20 - Managing the Evolution and Preservation of the Data Web at ISWC 2020
NUIG at TIAD: Combining Unsupervised NLP and Graph Metrics for Translation Inference	John P. McCrae and Mihael Arcan	Proceedings of the Globalex Workshop on Linked Lexicography (@LREC 2020)
A Comparative Study of Different State-of-the-Art Hate Speech Detection Methods in Hindi-English Code-Mixed Data	Priya Rani, Shardul Suryawanshi, Koustava Goswami, Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi, Theodorus Fransen and John Philip McCrae	Proceedings of the Second Workshop on Trolling, Aggression and Cyberbullying at LREC 2020
A Sentiment Analysis Dataset for Code-Mixed Malayalam-English	Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi, Navya Jose, Shardul Suryawanshi, Elizabeth Sherly and John Philip McCrae	Proceedings of 1st Joint SLTU (Spoken Language Technologies for Under-resourced languages) and CCURL (Collaboration and Computing for Under-Resourced Languages) Workshop at LREC 2020
Corpus Creation for Sentiment Analysis in Code-Mixed Tamil-English Text	Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi, Vigneshwaran Muralidaran, Ruba Priyadharshini and John Philip McCrae	Proceedings of 1st Joint SLTU (Spoken Language Technologies for Under-resourced languages) and CCURL (Collaboration and Computing for Under-Resourced Languages) Workshop at LREC 2020
Generating Grammars from lemon lexica for Questions Answering over Linked Data: a Preliminary Analysis	Philipp Cimiano, Basil Eil, Viktoria Benz and Mohammad Fazleh Elahi	Proc. of the Joint Workshop of NLIWOD and PROFILES, collocated with the International Semantic Web Conference
Bilingual Lexicon Induction across Orthographically-distinct Under-Resourced Dravidian Languages.	Bharathi Raja Chakravarthi, Navaneethan Rajasekaran, Mihael Arcan, Kevin McGuinness, Noel E. O'Connor and John P. McCrae	Proceedings of the Seventh Workshop on NLP for Similar Languages, Varieties and Dialects (VarDial 2020)

English WordNet: A new open-source wordnet for English	John P. McCrae, Ewa Rudnicka And Francis Bond	Lexicala Journal
Introduction to the Target Sense Verification for Word in Context (WiC-TSV) Challenge	Anna Breit, Artem Revenko, Kiamehr Rezaee, Mohammad Taher Pilehvar, Jose Camacho-Collados	6th SemDeep Workshop @ IJCAI-PRICAI 2020
WiC-TSV: Word-in-Context Target Sense Verification	Anna Breit, Artem Revenko, Kiamehr Rezaee, Mohammad Taher Pilehvar, Jose Camacho-Collados	https://competitions.codalab.org/competitions/23683
WiC-TSV: An Evaluation Benchmark for Target Sense Verification of Words in Context	Anna Breit, Artem Revenko, Kiamehr Rezaee, Mohammad Taher Pilehvar, Jose Camacho-Collados	Proceedings of the Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics (EACL)
Challenges of Definition Extraction in Spanish Legal Texts.	Karen Vázquez-Flores, Patricia Martín-Chozas, Elena Montiel-Ponsoda	<i>AICOL workshop at The 33rd International Conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems (JURIX 2019)</i> [Proceedings Pending]
A Domain Independent Semantic Measure for Keyword Sense Disambiguation	María Buey, Carlos Bobed, Jorge Gracia, Eduardo Mena	36th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium On Applied Computing (SAC'21) [short paper]

Appendix 2: Prêt-à-LLOD educational and scientific events

Event	Role of Prêt-à-LLOD	Partners	Date
2nd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge (LDK 2019)	Organization Committee	NUIG, GU	20-22.05.2019
3rd Datathon on Linguistic Linked Open Data	Organization Committee	NUIG, UNIZAR, GU	12-17.5.2019
Global WordNet Conference	Program Committee and Presentation of the papers "English WordNet 2019 — An Open-Source WordNet"	NUIG, DFKI	23-27.7.19

	<i>for English” and “OntoLex as a possible Bridge between WordNets and full lexical Descriptions”</i>		
Time Machine Conference	Participation	NUIG	10-11.10.2019
Singapore Symposium on Natural Language Processing	Participation	NUIG	31.10.2019
6th Italian Conference on Computational Linguistics. CLIC-it 2019	Participation	DFKI	13-15.11-2019
LT4All – International Conference on Language Technologies for All: Enabling Linguistic Diversity and Multilingualism Worldwide	Participation	DFKI	05-06.12.2019
Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and WordNet (MWE-WN 2019)	Participation and Presentation of two papers: “ <i>Identification of Adjective-Noun Neologisms using Pretrained Language Model</i> ” and “ <i>Using OntoLex-Lemon for Representing and Interlinking German Multiword Expressions in OdeNet and MMORPH</i> ”	NUIG,DFKI	02.08.2019
Workshop on eLexicography between Digital Humanities and Artificial Intelligence: Complexities in Data, Technologies, Communities	Workshop chairs and program committee members	NUIG,UNIBI	9.7.2019
31st Summer School on Logic, Language and Information	Course on “Introduction to Linked Open Data in Linguistics“	NUIG, DFKI	5-6.8.2019
Spring School LiSeH: Linked Data and the Semantic Web for Humanities research	Course on “Introduction to Linked Open Data in Linguistics”	NUIG,DFKI	24-27.04.2019
Workshop on Translation Inference Across Dictionaries (TIAD 2019)	Organization Committee and shared task organization; 4 presentations by Prêt-à-LLOD members	UNIZAR, GU, NUIG	20.05.2019
2nd Face2face Ontolex Meeting	Meeting of the Ontolex community	NUIG,UNIZAR,GU , UNIBI, DFKI	20.05.2019
Terminology & Ontology: Theory and Applications	Paper presentation: “Using Domain Specific Research Infrastructures in another	DFKI	6.-7.6.2019

	Domain: The Use of an Infrastructure for Lexicography in the field of Terminology”		
12th Conference on Recent Advances in Natural Languages Processing (RANLP 2019)	Presentation on Prêt-à-LLOD work on "Porting Multilingual Morphological Resources to OntoLex-Lemon"	DFKI	2.-4.9.2019
6th biennial conference on electronic lexicography, eLex 2019	Participation	NUIG, GUF, UNIZAR, DFKI	1-2.10. 2019
32nd International Conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems (JURIX 2019)	A poster on Prêt-à-LLOD was exhibited. Also a verbal description within Iberlegal (“NLP for the Legal Domain in the Iberian Peninsula”)	UPM	13.12.2019
7th Workshop on Linked Data in Linguistics	Organization Committee	GUF, DFKI, NUIG, UZAR	11.05.2020 (postponed because of COVID-19)
Workshop on Multimodal Wordnets	Organization Committee	DFKI	11.05.2020 (postponed because of COVID-19)
Globalex 2020 Workshop on Linked Lexicography, co-located at LREC 2020	Organization Committee	NUIG, UNIZAR	12.05.2020 (postponed because of COVID-19)
International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC 2020)	Participation, Paper Presentation	UNIZAR, GUF, SEM	Nov 1-6, 2020
Time Machine Conference	Participant https://www.timemachine.eu/tm2020-poster-wall/	NUIG	23 Nov 2020
Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Electronic Lexicons (MWE-LEX 2020) at COLING 2020	Organization Committee	NUIG	13th Dec 2020
First Workshop on Language Technology for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (LT-EDI-2021) at EACL 2021	Organization Committee	NUIG	19th Apr 2020
EuroLAN 2021 “Introduction to Linked Data for linguistics online training school”	Organising committee, steering committee, lecturers	UNIZAR, NUIG, GUF, DFKI	8-12 February 2021

